

Development of a set of software tools based on the effective radius approximation for simulating the kinetics of processes in the advanced thermonuclear reactors with D-³He fuel*

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the development of an alternative fuel cycle concept for fusion reactors with magnetic plasma confinement using D-³He fuel. Turning to this type of fusion fuel is believed to solve the key problems of thermonuclear fusion installations with traditional D-T fuel: the need to handle radioactive tritium and the so-called first wall problem arising from the intense flux of high-energy neutrons from the fusion reactor. In this connection, the problem arises of improving the accuracy of predicting the characteristics of the low-radioactive D-³He fuel cycle of fusion reactors with magnetic plasma confinement and determining ways to improve the efficiency of their operation, taking into account its peculiarities: higher realization temperatures, as a consequence, higher losses for bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation and the use of magnetic configurations with a high value of the parameter β (β – ratio of the plasma thermal pressure to the magnetic pressure). To solve this problem, it is necessary to have a set of computational-theoretical approaches to the modelling of processes in plasma and a detailed description of the plasma energy balance, based on modern data on the rates of thermonuclear reactions and a correct description of energy losses for bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation. The paper presents a set of software tools for calculating the rates of the main thermonuclear reactions based on the effective radius approximation, analytical parametrizations of losses for both types of radiation, taking into account relativistic effects, and for modelling the kinetics of processes occurring in the plasma, combined with the determination of the parameters of the Lawson criterion and the fusion triple product for different modes of D-³He fuel use (fully catalyzed or fully uncatalyzed modes, ³He self-supply mode, various power gain factors and various fusion reactor sizes).

Keywords

thermonuclear reactions, thermonuclear reaction rates, effective radius approximation, modelling of processes in D-³He plasmas

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Introduction

At the current stage of fusion research, the prospects for the practical implementation of controlled thermonuclear fusion remain linked to the D-T fuel cycle in magnetic confinement fusion systems – tokamaks and stellarators. Among these, tokamaks are currently the most advanced and promising (Velikhov and Ilgisonis 2021). The flagship of this direction is the international ITER project. However, due to increasing technical complexities, its launch, and, consequently the potential beginning of the era of practical fusion energy utilization, is expected after 2050. This circumstance, along with the search for ways to overcome the known drawbacks of the D-T fuel cycle, including the need for tritium breeding and the so-called first wall problem, has led to the development and justification of alternative fusion systems (Ryzhkov and Chirkov 2017), which include D-³He fuel fusion reactors. Advantages of the D-³He fuel cycle include:

- Significantly lower neutron flux compared to the D-T fuel cycle (at the same plasma density, but different operating temperatures corresponding to the triple product for these cycles). For this reason, D-³He fuel is often referred to as low-neutron or low-radioactivity.
- Higher power generation density. In a D-³He reactor, most of the thermonuclear energy is released in charged particles, whereas in a reactor with equimolar D-T fuel, 80% of the energy is carried away by neutrons. This circumstance indicates the possibility of constructing smaller reactors compared to D-T reactors of the same power.

Let's list the main disadvantages of the D-³He fuel cycle.

- Higher operating temperature. However, if we aim for the target parameter of a fusion reactor's operation in the form of the triple product (Velikhov and Ilgisonis 2021), this temperature lies in the range of 40–70 keV, depending on the fuel utilization modes (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2002; Chirkov 2006; Wurzel and Hsu 2022; Godes and Shablov 2023). This is significantly lower than the previous temperatures associated with the Lawson criterion, around 105–120 keV, and is already comparable to the triple product temperature for D-T reactors of $T \geq 10^8$ K (Velikhov and Ilgisonis 2021) or, according to the estimate provided in (Wurzel and Hsu 2022) $T = 14$ keV.
- Higher losses due to bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation. Minimizing the latter is one of the key tasks in justifying the practical feasibility of the D-³He concept. Solutions to this problem are known: increasing the reactor size in combination with the use of reflectors (Bekefi 1966; Trubnikov 1973; Stott 2005; Albajar et al. 2009) and/or using plasma confinement devices with a high, i.e., close to 1, parameter β (Ryzhkov and Chirkov 2017).

- The practical absence of Helium-3 (³He) isotope reserves on Earth. Currently, for practical purposes, such as cryogenics, it is obtained from the β -decay of tritium. This problem also has known solutions: mining ³He on the Moon, which has large reserves of this isotope; its production in D-D reactors; and implementing self-supply ³He operating modes (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2002; Chirkov 2006; Godes and Shablov; Ryzhkov and Chirkov 2017).
- Furthermore, a new method for obtaining ³He is emerging – from ordinary helium. Production of ordinary helium on a scale of up to 60 million m³ per year has recently begun at a Gazprom Group, the Amur Gas Processing Plant. It is known that the content of ³He in ordinary helium is $1.37 \cdot 10^{-6}$ (1.37 atoms of ³He per million atoms of ⁴He). In 2020, a subsidiary of Rosatom's enterprise "Kriogenmash" has developed and patented a new technology for extracting ³He and created a special installation for extracting ³He from liquid helium with an efficiency of 99.9%.
- Over the past few decades, a significant number of computational studies have been conducted to determine a key parameter of controlled thermonuclear fusion installations – the Lawson criterion. However, this work cannot yet be considered complete. The conducted research is either based on outdated data on reaction rates, or considers simplified models like the uncatalyzed D-D cycle, or does not account for the specifics of the D-³He cycle (significantly higher operating temperatures require the description of bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation losses, taking into account relativistic effects, which is not always done). Currently, the fusion triple product is considered a key characteristic of the controlled thermonuclear fusion process. However, there are very few studies on its determination for the D-³He fuel cycle, and only in isolated works is this criterion considered for a fully catalyzed operating mode of a fusion reactor with ³He self-supply. Thus, the task of increasing the accuracy of predicting the characteristics of the low-radioactivity D-³He fuel cycle of magnetic confinement fusion reactors remains relevant. This can be achieved through a set of advanced methods and algorithms for modeling plasma processes, which is the subject of this article. The complexity of the proposed approach lies in the detailed description of the plasma energy balance, based on modern data on thermonuclear reaction rates, and on the correct (taking into account relativistic effects where necessary) description of energy losses due to bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation.
- Based on the solutions of the kinetic equations for processes in isothermal plasma, it will be possible to investigate its parameters for three fuel ions: D, ³He and T). This includes accounting for the potential replenishment of ³He and impurity ions (p and ⁴He) removed from the reaction zone, for both a fully catalyzed D-D cycle and a cycle with ³He self-supply.

Consequently, the proposed approach will allow for comprehensive multi-variant calculations of the Lawson criterion and the fusion triple product criterion for both cycles, depending on the fusion reactor gain factor Q , the parameter β , the reactor aspect ratio and characteristics of synchrotron radiation reflectors.

Determination of the temperature dependence of the rates of main thermonuclear reactions based on the effective radius approximation (ERA)

As is known, the rates of thermonuclear reactions are among the key parameters necessary for a correct description of kinetic processes in fusion devices and for determining the target parameters of these devices – the Lawson criterion and the triple product criterion. In addition, reaction rates with neutron production are necessary for neutron plasma diagnostics (Bosch and Hale 1992). For this reason, since the 1950s, a large number of parameterizations for thermonuclear reaction rates have been developed, differing in both their methodological basis and the experimental material used. Currently, the most comprehensive and reliable are considered to be experimental data systematized in the NACRE II (Xu et al. 2013) and EXFOR (Zerkin and Pritychenko 2018) databases. A brief overview of approaches to determining thermonuclear reaction rates is provided in (Godes and Shablov 2023). In the present article, a model-independent approach to studying near-threshold, including resonant, nuclear reactions with charged particles – the effective radius approximation (Landau-Smorodinsky-Bethe approximation) (Bethe 1949; Landau and Lifshitz 1974) – is used to determine the rates of the main thermonuclear reactions. The ERA was first consistently applied to determine thermonuclear reaction rates in (Godes and Shablov 2023) using the $D + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow p + {}^4\text{He}$ reaction as an example, for which there were significant discrepancies in literature rates. In the present work, the parameters of the effective radius approximation for the rate of this reaction will be refined for the temperature range of 10–130 keV,

which is of most interest for fusion research. Furthermore, parameterizations for the rates of the $D + T \rightarrow n + {}^4\text{He}$ reaction and both channels of the D-D fusion reaction will be developed within this range. The ERA is based on an analytical parameterization of the reaction astrophysical factor $S(E)$, which is defined in a relatively simple analytical form and typically uses 6 parameters. In the next stage, the reaction rates are found by averaging $S(E)$ over the Maxwell distribution, which is a straightforward computational procedure that does not require significant time investment. The resulting data, as will be shown below, are in good agreement with the NACRE II database, which is currently considered the most accurate description of the available experimental data. However, they are more convenient for practical application. The NACRE II data are presented in tabular form and with a rather large step in the expected temperature range of the Lawson criterion, which complicates detailed calculations.

The key aspects of the effective radius approximation have been presented earlier in (Godes and Shablov 2023). The cross-section of the thermonuclear fusion reaction has the form (Nikitii 1983):

$$\sigma_r(E) = \frac{\pi}{k^2} \left(1 - e^{-2\text{Im}\delta_0(k)} \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\delta_0(k)$ is the nuclear-Coulomb phase shift in the elastic channel, which becomes complex in the presence of inelastic processes (Nikitii 1983). Within the effective radius approximation, expression (1) takes the form (Godes and Shablov 2023):

$$\sigma_r(E) = g \frac{4\pi}{3k^2} \frac{\beta(k)D(k)}{(\alpha(k) - 2h(k))^2 + (\beta(k) + D(k))^2}. \quad (2)$$

In (2), the following notation is used: $D(k) = 2\pi/(e^{2\eta}-1)$ is the Coulomb barrier penetration factor; η is the Coulomb parameter or Sommerfeld parameter:

$$\eta = \eta(k) = \frac{Z_1 Z_2 e^2 m_r}{\hbar^2 k} = \frac{1}{ka_c}, \quad a_c = \frac{\hbar^2}{Z_1 Z_2 e^2 m_r}, \quad (3)$$

a_c is the Bohr radius for the pair of fusing nuclei with reduced mass m_r ; $h(k) = \text{Re}\psi(i\eta) - \text{Im}\eta = \text{Re}\psi(i/ka_c) + \text{In}ka_c$, $\psi(z)$ is the logarithmic derivative of the gamma function or the ψ -function. The parameters $\alpha(k)$ and $\beta(k)$ define the nuclear-Coulomb phase shift $\delta_0(k)$ using the relation (Bethe 1949; Landau and Lifshitz 1974):

$$\frac{1}{a_c} D(k) \text{ctg}\delta_0(k) + \frac{2}{a_c} h(k) = -\frac{1}{a_0} + \frac{1}{2} r_0 k^2 = \frac{1}{a_c} (\alpha(k) - i \cdot \beta(k)), \quad (4)$$

where α_0 is the scattering length, r_0 is the effective radius, so that $\alpha(k) - i\beta(k) = \alpha_0 + a_1 \alpha_c^2 k^2 - i(\beta_0 + \beta_1 \alpha_c^2 k^2)$ with dimensionless parameters $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \beta_0, \beta_1$. Formula (4) is the Landau-Smorodinsky-Bethe approximation, wherein it is considered that the complex nature of $\delta_0(k)$ causes both the scattering length and effective radius to become complex. Additionally, the value $\beta(k)$ is positive, which is associated with the sign of the imaginary part of $\delta_0(k)$. In the general case, terms with k^4 and k^6 can be accounted for in the functions $\alpha(k)$ and $\beta(k)$, the coefficients of which are

proportional to the potential shape parameters. In formula (2), the spin factor $g = (2J+1)/[(2S_1+1)(2S_2+1)]$ is taken into account, which is equal to 2/3 for the reactions $D + T \rightarrow n + {}^4\text{He}$ and $D + {}^3\text{He} \rightarrow p + {}^4\text{He}$.

Table 1 presents the ERA parameters for the 4 main thermonuclear reactions, ensuring the best agreement with NACRE II data when determining the temperature dependence of the rates in the energy range of 10–130 keV. It should be noted that in the case of D-D synthesis reactions, the ERA can only determine the total inelastic

Table 1. Parameters for Effective Radius Approximation for 4 Fusion Reactions

Parameter	D+ ³ He→p+ ⁴ He	D+T→n+ ⁴ He	D+D→n+ ³ He	D+D→p+T
α_0	0.22412	0.3337	11.0758	4.9184
α_1	0.12387	0.05202	0.13868	-0.1245
α_2	0.00481	-0.0006	-0.0013	0.00045
β_0	0.03267	0.17254	0.73657	0.15122
β_1	0.00289	0.00596	0.06823	-0.0127
β_2	0.00067	0.00024	7.3E-05	0.0004

cross-section, so in this case, the application of ERA should be considered as a convenient parameterization of the cross-sections and rates of the reactions $D + D \rightarrow n + ^3\text{He}$ and $D + D \rightarrow p + T$.

The table presented here takes into account the potential shape parameters mentioned earlier. The quality of the developed parameterizations is illustrated in Figs 1, 2. It should be noted that for reactions 2–4, the parameterizations from work (Bosch and Hale 1992) are limited to a temperature range up to 100 keV, while the parameterizations from (Caughlan and Fowler 1988) for reactions 3–4 agree with NACRE II only in the temperature region below 50 keV.

Parametrization of energy losses due to Bremsstrahlung and synchrotron radiation

Thermonuclear plasma kinetics and determination of the triple product criterion

To describe energy losses due to bremsstrahlung radiation, the parametrization from (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2000) is used, which accounts for relativistic corrections for both electron-ion and electron-electron bremsstrahlung.

For the description of synchrotron radiation, the parametrization by Trubnikov (Trubnikov 1973) is employed, with relativistic corrections for electron-electron synchrotron

$$P_c = 3.12 \cdot 10^{-16} \langle Z \rangle \frac{1 + \langle Z \rangle}{2\beta} T^2 F(T) \Phi(t) n_i^2 = A_c \cdot n_i^2 \quad (5)$$

where temperature is measured in keV, and ion concentration n_i is in cm^{-3} . The following notation is used in (5): $\langle Z \rangle = \sum Z_j n_j / \sum n_j$ is the average ion charge, where Z_j is the charge of ions of the j -th type with concentration n_j ; $\beta = 2\mu_0 p / B_0^2$ is the ratio of the plasma thermal pressure $p = (1 + \langle Z \rangle) n_i T$ to the magnetic pressure $B_0^2 / 2\mu_0$, where μ_0 is the magnetic constant and B_0 is the induction of the

Figure 2. Temperature dependence of the reaction rate $D + D \rightarrow n + ^3\text{He}$.

radiation (Rose and Clark 1961; Albajar et al. 2009). We proceed from the traditional model of an isothermal plasma of constant density. Profile effects in plasma concentration and temperature were not considered at this stage (Stott 2005; Gott and Yurchenko 2022), this is planned to be carried out in the next phase of research. The specified parametrization of synchrotron radiation losses has the form

external magnetic field; $F(T) = K_3(m_e c^2/T) / K_2(m_e c^2/T)$ is the relativistic correction for synchrotron radiation (Rose and Clark 1961; Albajar et al. 2009), whose graph is shown in Fig. 3., $K_j(Z)$, $j = 2, 3$, are Macdonald functions, $\Phi(t)$ is Trubnikov universal coefficient for synchrotron radiation emission from a plasma bunch or a form factor (Trubnikov 1973), chosen as:

$$\Phi(t) = \Phi_{7/4}(t) = 120 \frac{t^{7/4}}{\sqrt{2.13 \cdot 10^{-3} a^*}} \left(\frac{T(1 + \langle Z \rangle)}{2\beta \langle Z \rangle n_e (\text{cm}^{-3})} \right), \quad a^* = \frac{a}{(1-r)(1+\chi)}, \quad (6)$$

Figure 3. Dependence of the function $F(T)$ on temperature.

where r is the reflection coefficient of synchrotron radiation, a is the characteristic size of the plasma bunch, and χ is the magnetic field non-uniformity parameter, which for a torus with radius R and the radius a of its generating circle is equal to:

$$\chi = \frac{2a}{R} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi t}}, \quad t = \frac{T}{m_e c^2}. \quad (7)$$

The parametrization (5)-(6) is applicable when the condition $\Phi_{7/4}(t) \ll 1$ is met, and its accuracy in the temperature range of interest of 10–100 keV is at the level of 20–30% (Trubnikov 1973).

To calculate the kinetics of processes occurring in the plasma, the equations presented in works (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2002; Godes and Shablov 2023) are used. Their formulation presumed the realization of a fusion reactor operating with a fully catalyzed D-D cycle, wherein the ^3He and T ions produced in D-D reactions are completely

$$\frac{n_D + n_{He} + n_T + n_p + n_\alpha + n_{imp}}{n_i} = \alpha + \alpha \gamma_{He} \delta + \alpha \gamma_T + \frac{n_p}{n_i} + \frac{n_\alpha}{n_i} + \frac{n_{imp}}{n_i} = 1 \quad (10)$$

It was assumed that the confinement times of “ash” ions (protons and α -particles) are equal, as in works (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2002; Godes and Shablov 2023), leading to $n_p = n_\alpha$. The parameter γ_T in (10) determines the equilibrium tritium concentration (neglecting its β -decay):

$$\gamma_T = \frac{0.5 \langle \sigma v \rangle_{DD \rightarrow pT}}{\langle \sigma v \rangle_{DT \rightarrow n\alpha}}. \quad (11)$$

The quantity n_{imp} sets the concentration of impurity ions from external sources (synchrotron radiation reflectors and the first wall of the fusion reactor) (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2002; Stott 2005).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we present the results of triple product calculations for tokamak reactors with various parameters to demonstrate the main capabilities of the developed software complex (Table 2).

Table 2 shows the concentrations of fuel ions D, ^3He , and T, the minimum values of the $n_i \tau T$ parameter depending

burned in the plasma (Stott 2005). One of these equations, which leads to the equilibrium concentration of ^3He in the self-supply ^3He regime, is written as

$$\frac{dn_{He}}{dt} = -\langle \sigma v \rangle_{DHe \rightarrow p\alpha} n_D n_{He} + 0.5 \langle \sigma v \rangle_{DD \rightarrow nHe} n_D^2 = 0, \quad (8)$$

$$n_{He} = \frac{0.5 \langle \sigma v \rangle_{DD \rightarrow nHe}}{\langle \sigma v \rangle_{DHe \rightarrow p\alpha}} n_D = \gamma_{He} n_D.$$

The triple product was determined by the traditional formula:

$$n_i \tau T = \frac{1.5(1 + \langle Z \rangle) T^2}{(f_c + Q^{-1}) A_f - A_{bre-i} - A_{bre-e} - A_c}. \quad (9)$$

The following notation is used in (9): $A_f = P_f/n_i^2$, P_f – fusion power density, given by the expression $A_f = \sum_{k,j,r,s} \langle \sigma v \rangle_{kj \rightarrow rs} Q_{kj \rightarrow rs} a_k a_j$, where $Q_{kj \rightarrow rs}$ is the Q -value of an exothermic reaction with the formation of ions of types r and s (in keV) (in the case of $k = j$, a multiplier of 0.5 is added), $a_k = n_k/n_i$ is the relative concentration of ions of type k , $A_{bre-i} = P_{bre-i}/n_i^2$ and $A_{bre-e} = P_{bre-e}/n_i^2$ where P_{bre-i} and P_{bre-e} are the density powers of bremsstrahlung radiation of electrons on ions and electrons on electrons, respectively, from work (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2000), A_c is given by formula (5), f_c is the fraction of fusion energy absorbed in the plasma, and Q is the power gain factor. The triple product is determined for various modes of D- ^3He fuel utilization, in particular for the fully catalyzed D-D cycle and the self-supply ^3He cycle. To close the calculation scheme, in which the control parameters are the quantities n_d and δ , the plasma ion balance equation is used:

on reactor parameters for fully catalyzed regimes, and the parameter δ , which defines the presence or absence of ^3He fueling: $n_{He} = \delta \gamma_{He} n_D$, so that in the self-supply regime $\delta = 1$, and in regimes with ^3He fueling $\delta > 1$ (Godes and Shablov 2023). When performing the calculations for all operating regimes, the electron concentration was taken as 10^{14} cm^{-3} , the power gain factor $Q = \infty$, and the con-

Table 2. Characteristics of Tokamak Reactors Using D- ^3He Fuel

Main parameters	1	2	3	4
β	0.5	1	0.5	1
a , m	2	2	3	2
R , m	3	3	4.5	3
r	0.65	0.92	0.65	0.92
B , T	2.27	1.77	2.40	1.83
δ	1	1	8.511	9.824
n_D/n_i	0.859	0.881	0.460	0.490
n_{He}/n_i	0.135	0.109	0.460	0.490
n_T/n_i	0.004	0.004	0.002	0.003
$(n_\alpha + n_p)/n_i$	0.002	0.006	0.078	0.085
$\langle Z \rangle$	1.14	1.11	1.50	1.50
T , keV	34	41	43	50
$n_i \tau T$, $\text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{keV} \cdot \text{s}$	$3.76 \cdot 10^{17}$	$1.31 \cdot 10^{17}$	$5.41 \cdot 10^{17}$	$7.48 \cdot 10^{16}$

concentrations of possible impurity ions were neglected. Considering the differences in the models used, the presented results are in general agreement with the results of works (Khvesyuk and Chirkov 2002; Stott 2005; Chirkov 2006), which considered tokamak reactors with similar characteristics, and demonstrate the theoretical possibility of achieving a controlled thermonuclear reaction in D-³He fueled reactors of relatively small sizes at relatively low plasma temperatures (around 40 keV) with commonly

considered values of reflection coefficients and parameter β . The broader capabilities of the developed software complex will be demonstrated in a separate work.

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